

Interactive Creation, Visualization and Exploration of Process Model Collections (Supplemental document)

To complement the use cases presented in Section 7.1 of the manuscript, this additional material provides step-by-step explanation, figures, and configuration details that illustrate how VISCoPro supports process exploration, filtering, and performance analysis. The aim is to give readers a deeper understanding of how the tool can be used in practice to answer business questions effectively, showcasing its flexibility, scalability, and integration of multiple analysis perspectives.

1. EFFECTIVENESS AND APPLICATION TO A REAL EVENT LOG

To evaluate VISCoPro’s effectiveness, we used one of the event logs of BPIC 2020 [1]. In that challenge, five event logs are available, containing information about the management of national and international travels, requests for travel permits and reimbursement of travel expenses at the Eindhoven University of Technology, where employees often travel to other universities or institutions to attend conferences or (project) meetings. We used the international travel dataset for this part of the evaluation, which contains 72,151 events, 6,449 traces and 753 trace variants. Among the seven main business questions and nine additional questions posed in the challenge, we focused on answering the three questions related to the international travel event log.

A. Finding differences between clusters of declarations

The business question posed in the BPIC reads as follows: “Are there differences between clusters of declarations, for example, between cost/centers/departments/projects, etc.?” We illustrate how VISCoPro simplifies and accelerates the exploration of this question. To address the question, we focused on departments, which are identified by the *case:Permit OrganizationEntity* attribute in the event log. There are more than 20 departments in the event log. A similar approach can be followed to analyze projects or centers.

Unlike most traditional tools that require manual filtering for each department, VISCoPro enables us to generate an entire collection of process variants in a single step. By selecting the *Attribute filter* in “Group by” mode and specifying the *case:Permit OrganizationEntity* attribute (R1.2, R1.3), VISCoPro automatically segments the event log and creates a collection of DFGs, one for each department, using absolute frequency as metric for nodes and transitions (R1.6). Figure S1 displays the configuration used and an excerpt of this collection.

Fig. S1. Excerpt of the DFG collection. They are created by grouping cases using the *case:Permit Organization Entity* attribute and applying the absolute frequency metric. In this configuration, all activities are shown (100%), but only the most frequent paths are rendered (0%).

The resulting DFGs reveal noticeable structural variation across departments. For example, Figure S2 shows the department with the highest number of unique activities (34 nodes), that

also contains an activity with the maximum absolute frequency of over 1,700. A detailed view of the DFG for this department is shown in Figure S3. However, others DFGs include activities with frequencies as low as one. The system directly presents these insights through recommended visualizations (R3.1), facilitating the comparison between more than 20 DFGs. This task would otherwise require significant manual effort from analysts.

Fig. S2. Identification of department with highest frequency and number of nodes (“organizational unit 65458”) using the Pattern Recommendation function. All activities (100%) and only the most frequent paths (0%) are shown.

Fig. S3. A detailed view of the DFG for the department “organizational unit 65458”. The maximum activity frequency is 1,748, and the DFG includes 34 nodes, although not all are visible with this configuration.

We can also analyze differences in control flow between departments by applying the case frequency metric (R1.6) and an *Attribute filter* using the *Keep selected* mode on top of the groups we already have (R1.2, R1.3). For example, filtering by activities *Start trip*, *End trip*, *Payment Handled*, and *Declaration Submitted by Employee*, we notice that in one department the percentage of cases in which *End trip* precedes *Declaration Submitted by Employee* is just around 50%, while in others it is above 90% (cf. Figure S4). Furthermore, that department also has a significantly higher number of cases in which *Payment Handled* precedes *Start trip*. This shows that this department follows in almost half of the cases a different flow than the others, where payment is declared and handled before the trip is performed. As shown in Figure S4, the grouping (R1.3) and collection visualization (R2.2) functionalities are key design choices aimed at supporting comparison, which proved to be very useful in this scenario. With more than 20 departments present in the log, the effort required was significantly lower compared to manually filtering the departments one by one.

As mentioned earlier, the event log contains data from more than 20 departments. Discovering such insights using a traditional process mining tool would have required manually filtering by each department individually. This approach is particularly powerful because the filters are applied simultaneously to the whole collection of DFGs rather than one at a time. This capability allows analysts to detect deviations and patterns on a large scale, which drastically reduces effort and error.

In the next section, we will use the same collection to analyze differences in time performance across departments. This will demonstrate how VISCoPro further supports time performance questions.

B. Calculating the throughput in different process steps

The business question posed in the BPIC reads as follows: “What is the throughput in each of the process steps, i.e., the submission, judgement by various responsible roles, and payment?”. To answer this question, we focus on identifying delays in the process steps and comparing their process complexity to understand the differences in throughput time between steps.

First, we explore the DFG corresponding to the entire event log without data manipulations, using low thresholds (R2.3, R2.4) to identify the most frequent activities in the process (cf. S5).

['organizational unit 65455'] - ['Start trip', 'End trip', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE']

['organizational unit 65454'] - ['Start trip', 'End trip', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE']

['organizational unit 65457'] - ['Start trip', 'End trip', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE']

Fig. S4. Excerpt from the DFG collection, with the identification of the DFG for the department “organizational unit 65454”, where two unusual behavioral patterns stand out. All activities (100%) and paths (100%) are shown. Red highlights exceptional patterns deviation from the norm observed in other departments.

This provides an overview of the most frequent execution path and helps identify the main steps of the process: *Permit SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE*, *Permit FINAL APPROVED by SUPERVISOR*, *Start trip*, *End trip*, *Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE*, *Declaration FINAL APPROVED by SUPERVISOR*, *Request Payment* and *Payment Handled*.

Once the main steps are identified, we apply the *Attribute filter* with the *Keep Selected* mode (R1.2, R1.3) and the *Follower filter* with its *Keep Selected Fragments* mode (R2.5) to the seven activities to obtain the DFGs of the seven intervals. Figure S6 displays only an excerpt of the seven generated fragments to illustrate the segmentation approach.

This functionality relies on fragment-based filtering, which enables exploration of process behavior by fragments of the process. Then, choosing the mean cycle time metric (R1.6) and selecting the activity threshold as zero (R2.3), we can directly obtain the throughput of each step (R2.2). For instance, the results reveal that the mean trip duration is five days, and the mean time to approve a permit is two days and to approve a declaration four days. Also, on average, the time it takes the employee to submit the declaration after a trip is 15 days.

This functionality relies on fragment-based filtering, which enables exploration of process behavior by fragments of the process. Then, choosing the mean cycle time metric (R1.6) and selecting the activity threshold as zero (R2.3), we can directly obtain the throughput of each step (R2.2). For instance, the results reveal that the mean trip duration is five days, and the mean time to approve a permit is two days and to approve a declaration four days. Also, on average, the time it takes the employee to submit the declaration after a trip is 15 days. For instance, Figure S7 provides a side-by-side comparison of four departments.

In contrast, the time to approve the permission ranges between one and 25 days, and the time

Fig. S5. Visualization of the most frequent process variant with only the most frequent paths between activities (0%).

Fig. S6. Application of Follower filter to split process fragments.

to approve the declaration ranges between one and 14 days (cf. Figure S8).

Unlike existing tools, VISCoPro supports a two-step grouping strategy (R1.4) to simplify analysis at scale. First, grouping by fragments of the process reduces the complexity of the DFG and narrows the focus to specific behavioral intervals. Then, grouping by attribute values creates collections of comparable, simple models. This combination facilitates the generation of several process models.

C. Identifying bottlenecks

The business question posed in the BPIC reads as follows: “Where are the bottlenecks in the process of a travel declaration?” R1.18 After exploring the process model corresponding to the entire event log, the fragment between *Declaration submitted by employee* and *Payment handled* was identified as the most relevant for analyzing potential bottlenecks, as it represents the period during which the employee is actively waiting for the reimbursement of expenses. To focus

Fig. S7. Excerpt from the DFG collection. Mean cycle time of “Request Payment” to “Payment Handled” in four departments.

Fig. S8. Excerpt from the DFG collection showing the minimum and maximum average durations of the declaration approval steps for departments “organizational unit 65477” and “organizational unit 65488”: one with an average of one day and another with an average of fourteen days.

on this part of the process, we use a *Follower filter* with the *Keep selected fragments* mode (R2.5). Next, we split the event log in two subsets by using the *Attribute filter* with the two types of final approvals that appear in the log: by supervisor, and by director (R1.2, R1.3). This results in two DFGs, allowing us to compare the behavior in each case (R2.2) (cf. Figure S9).

Due to the high complexity of the DFGs, we apply another *Attribute filter* to both, retaining only four key activities (*Declaration submitted by employee*, *Payment handled*, *Declaration*

Fig. S9. Fragment of the process between *Declaration submitted by employee* and *Payment handled*, selected using the Follower filter in *Keep selected fragments* mode (R2.5).

FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR and *Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR*) in order to analyze the relationships between them more clearly (R1.2, R1.3). Figure S10 shows that when the final approval is done by the director, the percentage of cases in which the employee has to resubmit the declaration is higher (31% vs 22%) and the times it takes between resubmissions is also higher (eleven days against eight days). This suggests differences in the process depending on who does the final approval.

We further explore the cases in which the final approval is done by the supervisor by applying again the *Attribute filter* for the four types of approvals and six types of rejections that may apply to the declaration (R1.2, R1.3). This results in 10 DFGs, each showing the behavior under a specific outcome (R2.2). Although approvals show little variation, rejections exhibit a wider range of time between resubmissions (from six to 13 days). Additionally, we notice that the time between the last submission and the payment handled is slightly lower when there is previous rejection. In conclusion, no clear bottlenecks are identified in the process, but hints towards potential delays that are worth exploring are figured out.

REFERENCES

1. B. van Dongen, "BPI Challenge 2020," 4TU.ResearchData (2020).

Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE - Payment Handled - ['Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR'] - ['Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR']

Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE - Payment Handled - ['Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR'] - ['Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR']

(a) DFGs with case frequency as metric.

Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE - Payment Handled - ['Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR'] - ['Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR']

Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE - Payment Handled - ['Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR'] - ['Declaration SUBMITTED by EMPLOYEE', 'Payment Handled', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by SUPERVISOR', 'Declaration FINAL_APPROVED by DIRECTOR']

(b) DFGs with mean cycle time as metric.

Fig. S10. Comparison of DFGs for declarations approved by supervisor and director, filtered to highlight key activities and their relations. All activities (100%) and paths (100%) are shown.